

PREPARATION OF FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS FOR INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES

Dexqonov Baxodir Burxonovich

Kokand State Pedagogical Institute, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10162732>

Annotation: he article describes the issues of preparing future physical education teachers for innovative activities, organizing the content of physical education lessons on a scientific basis, modernizing its organizational and technological foundations, developing future development trends, in which the purpose of innovative activity is determined by society and its result is related to the interests of society, guiding young people towards social relations.

Keywords: innovation, physical education teacher, technology, activity, planning, evaluation.

It is known that the qualities and qualities of a person are formed in the process of functioning and are the result of activity. Therefore, it is necessary to instill in teachers the psychology of aspiration for innovation and the constant need for independent reading. Because novelty gives a person more pleasure than glory.

In the "National Training Program" of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the "filling of educational institutions with specially trained qualified pedagogical personnel is provided, based on competition in their activities the environment is brought into being," he said. One of the main factors in creating a competitive **labor environment**.

By directing teachers to innovative activities and preparing them for this activity, it consists in applying modern pedagogical technologies to the educational process, guaranteeing student-student knowledge and achieving educational efficiency. In the process of substantive reform of the educational system, a state policy is carried out with stability on improving the reputation, responsibility and professional skills of pedagogical personnel. In this regard, the main task is to update the activities of the teacher and introduce innovations into the **educational process**.

Like specialists in any other field, physical education teachers have a level of professional training in their knowledge, it is assessed by skills and qualifications, creative potential and professional competence, which is reflected in its non-traditional thinking.

The innovative activity of a physical education teacher is manifested in a culture of creative approach, creative active likeness, technological and methodological preparation for the introduction of innovation, new thinking,

treatment. Innovation is absorbed in the process of innovations, innovations, literally education during the period of activity. Therefore, the introduction of innovations in the educational system into the pedagogical process is carried out in several **stages**:

- analysis of the existing pedagogical problem;
- design of the educational system being designed;
- planning, organizing and controlling changes and innovations in the pedagogical process.

The purpose of preparing physical education teachers for innovative activities is to improve the teacher's striving for innovation, the formation of skills and competencies for independent work on himself, the ability to conduct lessons and extracurricular activities using modern pedagogical technologies, interactive **techniques**.

Innovation activity is the creation of a new technological process or a new improved product, using scientific research, development, conducting pilot work or other scientific and technological achievements. The original content of innovation activity is the formation of a new technology in practice, the result of which is the *fao liyat*, which is aimed at transforming the invention that arose as innovation into a project, a project into technology.

There are a number of psychological barriers to preparing a teacher for innovative activities. The first of these is that it is very difficult for shi to go beyond the limits of the activity that the teacher himself is used to, that is, when there is not enough creativity in teachers, another reason is that new and unknown things always cause chills and peril in people. Therefore, a new generation of competitive specialists is envisaged, in particular, in the training of physical education teachers, to prepare personnel with the ability to put forward promising tasks, to be able to emigrate them, to a culture of high thinking and to be able to independently use scientific and technical and social political information.

The study of the processes of innovation, their functions, laws of development, mechanisms and technologies for its implementation, pedagogical foundations of the principles of management – makes it possible to organize the activities of the teacher in a state corresponding to the world templates. In this case, the activity of the physical education teacher innovation requires the use of certain norms that determine the effect of innovating. Future physical education teacher preparation for innovation activities goes as follows: predicting the success of the intended novelty in aggregate and its individual stages; comparing

the novelty with other innovations, choosing its effectiveness from them, determining their most significant and level of accuracy; checking the degree of success of the implementation of the novelty; assessing the ability of the innovation implementation of the organization.

In this, the innovative activity of the teacher is also reflected in his personal competence.

The teacher demonstrates the following abilities in innovative activities:

- applies creative motivation in classroom activities, evaluates professional activities;

- cooperates with the creative interaction of students;

- organizes its work with perseverance, responsibility and honesty;

- innovation determines the need for activity;

- prepares to engage in creative activities;

- align personal goals with innovation activist-yat, etc.

In innovative activities, the teacher should be a progressive, productive creative person, a wide-ranging interest, a rich inner world, revenge for pedagogical innovation. Innovational activity is made up of motivational, technological and reflexive parts. Preparation of the teacher for this activity is carried out in two directions: formation of innovative preparation for the perception of novelty and training to act in a new way. Of particular importance in the organization of innovative activities is the cognitive activity of learners and its management.

As a result of the innovative activity of the physical education teacher, physical fitness, individual and psychological characteristics of students, their area of motives are studied in the environment, methodological complexes are created that provide a continuous didactic system designed for physical conditioning at school and extracurricular activities; educational activities advertising various competitions, healthy lifestyles: conversations, evenings, sports shows are organized, students' interests in sports are taken into account, sports clubs are involved, physical, mental and intellectual abilities of the students are cultivated; pedagogical and psychological environments in the family, classroom and school are studied in detail and their cooperation is developed.

The innovative activity of the teacher is aimed at determining the transformation of reality, the solution of its problems and methods. Hence, the change in the subject-subject relationship between the teacher and the learner as an example of new communication is one of the conditions of innovational

activity. The new relationship should be free from such elements as qistovs, submission to judgment, as in tradition. They need to be built in the form of equal cooperation, mutual management, mutual assistance.

Used literature:

1. Ashmarin B.A. Biomechanical indicators. - M.: "Fizkul-sport, "2014. -S. 276.
2. Z.V. Semenova Innovative technologies in education: Society and problems .// " Internet News Information. " Т., 2012, 2.
3. Nazirjonovich, X. Z., & o'rmonjonovich, I. F. (2023). Physical Education In Higher Educational Institutions Problems Of Formation Of Professional Skills On The Basis Of Science And Practice Ytegration In The Training Of Teaching Staff. Journal of Positive School Psychology, 870-876.
4. O'rmonjonovich, I. F. (2022). Problems of Development of Physical Culture and Sports after Independence. Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture, 3(12), 58-62.
5. Yakubjonov I. A., Bektemirovich, N. B., & Makhmudovich, G. A. (2022). The development of muscle mass as a means of increasing the immune system of a person. International journal of social science & interdisciplinary research issn: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(11), 62-67.
6. Akramjonovich, Y. I., & Ismailovna, Y. F. (2022). Pedagogical Conditions That Ensure The Successful Development Of Physical Fitness Of Modern Youth. Journal of Positive School Psychology, 6(10), 4495-4499.
7. Yakubjonov, I. A., & Yakubjonova, F. I. (2023). Stol tennis o 'yini orqali insonning tez anglash qobiliyatini rivojlantirish. Scientific progress, 4(1), 254-259.
8. Якубжонов, И. А., & Шокиров, Ш. Г. (2022). Кувватов У.Т "Развитие воспитательной работы в студенческой футбольной команде.". In International conference: problems and scientific solutions (Vol. 1, pp. 140-147).
9. Yakubjonov, I. A., Yakubjonova, F. I., & Azizov, M. A. (2022). The role of physical education and sports in the development of the human organism. In International conference: problems and scientific solutions (pp. 124-130).
10. Yakubjonov, I., Azizov, M., & Yakubjonova, F. (2022). Development of physical training and sports in the formation of a healthy young generation. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 1, 170-173.
11. Arabboyev Qakhramon Tohirjonovich. (2022). Adaptation of athlete students to student life. International journal of social science & interdisciplinary research issn: 2277-3630 Impact Factor: 7.429, 11(11), 272-276.

12. Arabboyev Qahramon Tohirjonovich. (2022). The importance of functional training in the athlete training system. International journal of social science & interdisciplinary research issn: 2277-3630 Impact Factor: 7.429, 11(11), 261-264.
13. Arabboyev, Q. T. "Sportchilarni tayyorlashda funksional tayyorgarlikning ahamiyati: 10.53885/edinres. 2022.75.29.012 QT Arabboyev." Научно-практическая конференция. 2022.
14. Ismoilovna, Y. F., & Farhodjon o'g'li, Y. A. (2023). Voleybol texnikasiga
15. o'rgatishning umumiy asoslari. Youth, science, education: topical issues, achievements and innovations, 2, 22-28.

